

Access Control Using Mobile Verification System For Cloud

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ABSTRACT

Cloud Computing is a large-scale distributed computing scenario which is based on web services on the Internet. Internet has many security defects because of its receptivity. It also has many other attacks and threats. Most challenging issues in cloud computing are access control and data security because cloud user store their sensitive data and information on cloud provider's servers which is not trusted area of data owner. In this paper we proposed a access control mechanism for data access in cloud environment. It works in two steps, the first step authenticate the user using mobile verification method and in second step provides data access control using role/ group based permission system .

Keywords- cloud computing; internet; security; access control; data security;

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing is an Internet-based computing solution where shared resources/services are provided like electricity distributed on the electrical grid. The cloud computing provides basically three type of services. *Software as a service (SaaS)* in which the cloud service provider provides applications and software over a network. Google Docs[1], Facebook[2], Gmail[3], are the example of SaaS. *Platform as a Service(PaaS)* provides application or development platform in which user can create their own application that will run on the cloud, example of PaaS are Microsoft's Azure[4], Google's App Engine(App Engine)[5], and third type of cloud service is Infrastructure as a service (IaaS), the whole cloud infrastructure, including servers, routers, hardware based load-balancing, firewalls, storage and other network equipment is provided by the IaaS provider[6] e.g Amazon S3[7], Amazon EC2[8]. The cloud computing can be deployed as *public cloud*, *private cloud*, *hybrid cloud* and *community cloud*. Public clouds are publicly available and can serve multiple tenants, examples of public Cloud: Google App Engine, Microsoft Windows Azure[9], IBM Smart Cloud[10] and Amazon EC2 while private cloud is typically a tailored environments with dedicated virtualized resources for particular organization examples of private clouds are Eucalyptus[11], Ubuntu Enterprise Cloud – UEC[12], Amazon VPC (Virtual Private Cloud)[13], VMware Cloud Infrastructure Suite[14], Microsoft ECI data center[15]. Similarly, community cloud is tailored for a particular group of customers Google Apps for Government, Microsoft Government Community Cloud are the example of community cloud. Hybrid cloud is composed of multiple clouds like Windows Azure (capable of Hybrid Cloud), VMware vCloud (Hybrid Cloud Services).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To overcome from security threats during access the services or applications many researchers has presented effective mechanisms and methods for access control . Paper [16] proposed an innovative mechanism to achieve flexible access control during co-ordinate resource sharing in enterprise grid environment. The mechanism proposes a new model for users, resources and their relationships which define co-ordination and access control. The solution targets to satisfy the demands usually found in enterprise environments with respect to controlled sharing of resources . Paper [17] presents a Key-Chain-Web access control mechanism which expands the usability of the mechanism in different scenarios. The Key-Chain-Web mechanism is based on three entities Users (keys), Resources (chains) and Relationships (webs). In addition, chain members representing relationship among users and resources, particularly in case of a collaborative environment where sharing may be achieved through members. [17].

Paper [18] promotes an authorization model based on both role-based access control and security labels. The security labels represent colors and these colors are used to control the access to data sharing, to virtual machines, network resources, etc. Paper [19] promotes an authorization scheme for the cloud computing

based on session keys shared between the cloud services and the users in order to be able to access to the protected resources.

Paper [20] propose an authorization architecture based on UCON suitable for the cloud computing. The main contribution of this proposal is the inclusion of a negotiation model in the authorization architecture to enhance flexibility of the access control on the cloud services. When the access requested mismatches with access rules, it allows users to get a second access choice through negotiation in certain circumstances, instead of refusing access directly.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The most challenging ongoing research in cloud computing are access control and data security, because of users outsourcing their sensitive data to cloud providers servers which is not trusted area of data owner. To tackle this problem, we proposed a access control mechanism for data access in cloud environment.

4. DESIGN OF ACCESS CONTROL MECHANISM WITH MOBILE VERIFICATION

Step-1 A. User authentication We used a simple select unique statement for matching email and password with mobile generated code. For security reasons, an MD5 hash [21] of concatenation of email and password was stored and compared. Below figure shows user authentication

Step-2 Access Control of Data and Application The users are split into groups and permissions are assigned to the group, not the individual user, as shown below

$G_1, G_2, G_3, \dots, G_n$ are groups of users, $T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_n$ are Tasks and P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n are the permissions that are given particular group have role assigned to access particular task e.g $G_1 \rightarrow T_1$ with permission P_1 , which we can write as $G_1 \rightarrow [(T_1), P_1]$ and $G_2 \rightarrow [(T_1, T_2), P_2]$ means group G_2 have the right to access the tasks T_1 and T_2 with permission P_2 and so on.

Here we tried implement group based security around the $USER \leftrightarrow ROLE \leftrightarrow ROLE$ TASK \leftrightarrow TASK tables that provides sufficient flexibility. The two significant reasons are:

- Permissions can be maintained on a single screen.
- Permission can be verified with a single lookup on the ROLE-TASK table using ROLE_ID and TASK_ID at run-time

There are three entities within this model as is understood from the name:

A. User Users of resources in cloud are identified by a unique key at the abstract level which may be username/password tokens or certificates like X.509 [23] or Kerberos [24] during implementation.

B. Resource/Task Resources within a Cloud are identified by the following attributes:

- **Masterkey** the key of the owner or the user with all control over the resource.
- **protected operations list** a list of operation names that must be authorized for execution over the resource.
- **max access level** the maximum levels into the web hierarchy to look while authorization for protected operations over the resource.

C. Relationship Relationships among user and tasks are identified by access rights(Permissions). By using CRUD matrix [25] insertion, deletion and updation of permissions are very easy and retrieval may be improved.

Our current design Here the main screen usernames, along with the set of permissions are displayed for each user.

The permissions allowed for the user have a green mark in front of them while those which are forbidden have a red mark in front of them. By clicking on the user name link, individual set of permissions could be seen.

The Admin Screen- Here the admin can manage the set of permissions for different user. The accessibility levels are as described before, that is, are group based, role based and are defined for individual user. The access control for a group are predefined which may be changed, to apply to all users within that group, thus saving the time to go through defining the access control for individual user.

For individual user- Once the user has been identified the USER record will supply the USER-GROUP identity which is all that is needed to access the PERMISSIONS table. Once the user name has been clicked, the set of permissions pertaining to that user could be accessed which is actually done by accessing a master key assigned to every user

For group permissions-

- Any change made to a group's permissions will automatically be inherited by all members of that group.
- A new role may be added and accordingly the set of permissions may be defined for that role..

Manage permissions- Here the set of permissions could be added or deleted as per the need of the user. A new permission could be added by simply specifying a unique key and the name of the permission.

5. CONCLUSION

It is possible to maintain such a complex database for such a requirement, in overall, the framework serves as an easy means to define access control in a multi-user environment as the need for group based and role based access are taken care of.

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